

Comparison of EGNOS vs. GPS and analysis of Bluetooth 5.1 DRI coverage

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Abstract – The drone market is currently booming and is expected to continue to grow. To ensure that safety is not compromised at very low altitudes, the TRACE project was created, funded by the GSA EGNOS Adoption in Aviation grant, whose aim was to design and develop a smart beacon for UAS/drones that uses the corrections provided by an EGNOS receiver, to improve the positioning accuracy and thus the safety of drone operations at very low altitudes. The location data is sent to a near smartphone through Bluetooth (direct remote identification) and to U-Space through Internet (network identification). This document evaluates the quality of the EGNOS receiver compared to a GPS receiver, and the coverage and performance of Bluetooth technology uses in the smart beacon for broadcasting the location data. The results obtained show the improvement of EGNOS over GPS and the range of up to 1 km in the reception of locating broadcasting messages using long range Bluetooth technology.

Keywords – EGNOS, DRI, UAV, drones, VLL, GNSS, EGNOS, direct remote identification.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last years, the Very Low Level (VLL) traffic has increased considerably, and the current trend is on the rise. According to estimations, revenues from drone-based services are expected to exceed 150 million euros by 2023 [1]. This situation could be a problem for airspace management in the future.

On the other hand, the association that develops and maintains standards for the European aerospace and defence industry (ASD-STAN), published in December 2020 the prEN 4709-002 [2], a standard indicating the use of direct remote identification (DRI) for drones, which will be effective soon. The aim of this is to be able to quickly identify unmanned aircrafts that in the past were previously unidentified and could cause conflict.

In this framework, TRACE project (<https://www.trace-project.com>) was proposed to maintain the safety level at a VLL airspace using an EGNOS-based smart beacon, which sends its information (position, status, and identification) broadcasting locally using Bluetooth (direct remote

identification) and to the services of U-Space via Internet using cell-phone network infrastructure (network identification).

The reason for developing a smart beacon based on EGNOS [3] is because it allows to increase the accuracy and integrity of the GPS, which is very essential to allow the integration of many unmanned aircrafts in the airspace. In addition, EGNOS provides a level of integrity called protection levels that allows the user to be sure in which volume the drones is with a very high probability.

Therefore, this whitepaper aims to compare the GNSS system of the smart beacon augmented with EGNOS versus a GNSS system with only GPS. And on the other hand, to analyse the performance and coverage of this smart beacon developed with Bluetooth 5.1 Long Range. Next Section explains the setup used for the experiments. Section III explains in detail the obtained results in a number of outdoor flying experiments with a drone. Finally, Section IV briefly details the most important conclusions of this work.

II. PREPARATION OF THE EXPERIMENTS

For the experiments, the smart beacon developed within TRACE project and an u-blox GNSS system have been used.

The smart beacon is formed by a Bluetooth 5 Long Range (BT5 LR) microcontroller, and two modules that are plugged: a GNSS EGNOS module and a 4G LTE-CAT M1 Modem module (with an internal microcontroller), see Figures 1 and 2.

The main functions for this board are to obtain data from the GNSS receiver and send it through BT5 LR, according to the DRI protocol [2], and LTE Module to send the data to U-Space Services (through a Backbone server). For the experiments explained in this study, the part of the U-Space (network identification) has not been considered since the experimental results have been mainly focused on evaluating the direct remote identification (DRI) functionality and performance.

Fig. 1 Block diagram of smart beacon

Fig. 2 Electronic boards of smart beacon (left). Smart Beacon TRACE ready to be integrated on a drone (right)

A. EGNOS vs GPS experiment

In this experiment, the GNSS receiver (u-blox) with only GPS versus a GNSS receiver with EGNOS (smart beacon) are compared; see Figure 3. Specifically, the objective is to measure the variation of the position of both receivers taken into account that they are fixed in a relative position that allows to compare the obtained results.

The features of the receiver are the following:

GNSS Receiver	Model	Antenna
GPS only	ZED-F9P-01B	ANN-MS-0-005 ublox
GPS+EGNOS	Septentrio mosaic-X5	Triple Band GNSS Antenna with L-band

Table 1. Used GNSS receiver models

Fig. 3 Setup of first experiment, right GPS receiver(ublox), left EGNOS receiver (smart beacon).

The test procedure was as follows:

- The two GNSS receivers were placed side by side over a table outside and with good sky visibility.
- After both receivers are switched on and 5 minutes are waited to get enough satellites to obtain a good and stable position.
- After this point, logging for both receivers is started for 10 minutes.
- Finally obtained data is downloaded on a PC to analyse the data.

B. DRI coverage experiment

In this experiment, it was analysed the performance of BT5 LR of the TRACE smart beacon. Specifically, it was evaluated how it changes the RSSI of the Bluetooth in a range of 1km at different heights up to the legal flight limit of UAVs for VLL flights, and the reception rate. To carry out this experiment, it was necessary to attach the smart beacon to a UAV/drone (see Figure 5) and receive Bluetooth data with a smartphone with an app for DRI compatible with prEN 4709-002 standard (see Figure 4).

The material used for this experiment was the following:

Material	Model
Smartphone	Samsung Galaxy S10+
App for receive DRI	Open Drone ID App
Smart beacon	CC2652R Texas instruments
Bluetooth sender	
Bluetooth antenna	ANT-2.4-CW-RCT - Linx
UAV	DJI Matrice 600

Table 2. Materials for the Bluetooth experiments

Fig. 4 Open Drone ID App

Fig. 5 DJI Matrice 600

The Bluetooth sender was configured as shown in the following table:

Bluetooth Mode	Sending Rate
125kbps Coded PHY (S=8)	100ms

Table 3. Bluetooth configuration

Fig. 6 Setup beacon with Matrice 600

The test procedure was as follows:

- The UAV pilot configured five automatic flights at different heights 40m,60m,80m,100m,120m; in a straight line with a distance of 1km over flat ground (see Figure 7).

Fig. 7 Place of flight and distance flown

- The beacon was turned on and the smartphone was placed at point 0 of the drone's path, vertically and at a height of 1.6m above the ground.
- After that it was checked that Bluetooth data were receiving correctly through the Open Drone ID App, the logging was enabled, and the pilot started the mission.
- The UAV performed two flights per altitude.

Fig. 8 Diagram of the second experiment

- At the end of each flight, the log of Bluetooth App was saved on the computer for the analysis.

III. RESULTS

Given all the logs, the data necessary for the analysis were extracted and in the case of the DRI coverage experiment, data processing and filtering was necessary.

A. EGNOS vs GPS experiment results

To make a more compressible comparison between the GPS receiver and the receiver with EGNOS, given latitude and longitude position in WGS84, the difference of the distance (m) obtained at each time instant with respect to the initial point has been calculated using the inverse Vincenty's formulas [4] (which give an accuracy of 0.5mm).

The following figure shows the variation of the position (without height) of the GPS and EGNOS receivers for 10 minutes:

Fig. 9 Difference in position relative to the starting point. GPS vs EGNOS

As it can be seen in the above figure, the difference is clear, the position variation in the GPS receiver is much larger than in the EGNOS receiver. The position variation from the mean is almost 10 times higher in GPS than in EGNOS.

	GPS receiver	EGNOSS receiver
Mean Position (μ)	0.787 m	0.14m
Variance Position (σ^2)	0.1734 m	0.0075 m
Maximum deviation from the mean position	1.102m	0.127m

Table 4. Position XY variation statistics. GPS vs EGNOS

Regarding the altitude, the following figure shows the altitude variation of GPS and EGNOS for 10 minutes.

Fig. 10 Altitude (HAE) GPS vs EGNOS

	GPS receiver	EGNOSS receiver
Mean Altitude (μ)	72.257m	71.898m
Variance Altitude (σ^2)	0.818m	0.059m
Maximum deviation from the mean altitude	2.455m	0.428m

Table 5 Altitude variation statistics. GPS vs EGNOS

As the last case, the difference is clear between the two receivers. The maximum deviation from the mean in altitude is up to 6 times greater in GPS than EGNOS, with a difference of up to 2,455m. It is important to point out that the two receivers were fixed on a table during the whole experiment.

B. DRI coverage experiment

Once the Bluetooth data was obtained, the timestamp, RSSI and the distance from the receiver were extracted to analyse how the RSSI changes with respect to the distance and reception frequency of the Bluetooth messages.

For a better analysis of the data, it was decided to filter out the high frequencies and to make a moving average, as shown in the following figure.

Fig. 11 Filtered RSSI height 60m

Next, a tendency curve was made with polynomial extrapolation for heights at 40, 60, 80, 100 and 120m.

Fig. 12 RSSI in relation to distance. Height: 40m

Fig. 13 RSSI in relation to distance. Height: 60m

Fig. 14 RSSI in relation to distance. Height: 80m

Fig. 15 RSSI in relation to distance. Height: 100m

Fig. 16 RSSI in relation to distance. Height: 120m

As it can be observed in Figures 12-16, the signal power decreases with the distance and oscillates. This oscillation is due to the combination of the incident wave and the wave reflected by the earth's surface [5], which is received by the smartphone. This fact could be verified theoretically with the flat earth propagation model [6], but it is beyond the scope of this whitepaper.

To compare the RSSI level of all heights in relation to distance, all their trend lines have been plotted on the following figure:

Fig. 17 RSSI- height comparison

As expected, the RSSI level is better at lower UAV height at closer distances (around -84dBm for 40m of altitude, against -93dBm for 120 m of altitude), but at 1 km the differences between different heights are smaller (around -98dBm and -99dBm for all heights). At 1km the signal is at the limit to be detected (-100dBm), so from this distance there could be reception problems.

Regarding the reception time of Bluetooth messages, the same processing and filtering procedure as RSSI has been carried out (the data above 2s were filtered).

Fig. 18 Time between messages. Height: 40m

Fig. 19 Time between messages. Height: 60m

Fig. 20 Time between messages. Height: 80m

Fig. 21 Time between messages. Height: 100m

Fig. 22 Time between messages. Height: 120m

The minimum possible reception time would be 0.1s, which is the sending rate at which the smart beacon was configured (Table 3. Bluetooth configuration), so that is the minimum time it can be observed in the above graphs. In all height cases, the reception time increases with distance and oscillates as in the RSSI.

The following figure shows the bluetooth message reception time trend lines of all heights in relation to distance.

Fig. 23 Time between messages - height comparison

As it can be observed in the last figure and considering the whole range of heights at 0m distance the reception time is around 0.27s, and for 1 km the time varies between 0.38s and 0.58s which is enough for direct remote identification purposes.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a set of experiments to compare the EGNOS receiver of TRACE smart beacon versus a generic GPS receiver and another survey to analyse DRI coverage of the smart beacon using Bluetooth 5.1 Long Range, for different heights up to 120m and up to a distance of 1km has been presented.

The accuracy and stability of the EGNOS receiver has been found to be better than the GPS. This makes it ideal for critical applications where a high stability is required. Furthermore, if it is considered that EGNOS provides integrity information with the protection levels, which together with the accuracy and stability, provides an additional value to safely integrate a greater number of unmanned aircrafts in the airspace.

Regarding the DRI coverage, it has been possible to verify that up to 120m height and up to 1km away it is possible to receive DRI messages of smart beacon using Bluetooth 5.1 Long-range, with a good reception frequency.

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